

Checklist of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Omsk Region (Russia)

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Abstract

An annotated check-list of the longicorn beetles of Omsk Region is given. The list based on literature data and collecting materials of authors. 41 species are new to the fauna of Omsk Region.

Keywords

Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Fauna, Omsk Region, West Siberia, Biodiversity

Introduction

The beetle fauna of the Omsk region has not been studied enough and is very fragmentary. The first data on the beetles of the region (mainly in the vicinity of Omsk) we can find in the work of S.D. Lavrov (Lavrov 1927), where 41 species of longicorn

beetles are presented. T.F. Kosheleva mentions 20 species of longicorn beetles from the collection of the Omsk State Museum of local history (Kosheleva 2003), but in a general way, without indicating the label data and the number of specimens. In addition, the definitions of some specimens needed to be clarified. One species – *Purpuricenus globucilollis* Mulsant, 1839 was included in the local Red Book (Knyazev et al. 2015) as *Purpuricenus kaehleri* Linnaeus 1758. All these materials were reprocessed by us, partially redetermined and included in the text of this work.

Material and methods

The article is based on materials collected by the authors in the period from the early 1980s to 2022. We collect specimens in all natural zones - from the taiga in the north to the steppes in the south of the Omsk region, with the maximum coverage of various biotopes (Figs 1–3). In addition, we have processed materials from the collections of the Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Novosibirsk), the Omsk State Museum of local history (Omsk), and fellow entomologists from the Omsk Region - O.N. Kholodov (Krasnyi Oktyabr', Omsk Region) and A.A. Sal'nik (Ermak, Omsk Region).

The following abbreviations are used in the text for the places of storage of the collection material: ISEA – collection of the Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Novosibirsk); OGKM – collection of the Omsk State Museum of local history (Omsk); SKSS – collection of S.A. Knyazev and S.M. Saikina (Omsk); KPO – collection of K.B. Ponomarev (Omsk); VTO – collection of V.Yu. Teploukhov (Bolshie Uki, Omsk region); OKO – collection of O.N. Kholodov (Krasnyi Oktyabr', Cherkulak district, Omsk region); ASO – collection of A.A. Salnik (Ermak, Novovarshevsky district, Omsk region). Species firstly reported for the Omsk Region are marked by asterisk.

List of collecting sites (in alphabetical order):

624 km – Lyubinsky district, 4 km NW of Mokshino vill., rail station 2624 km, 55°19'19.18"N, 72°16'10.43"E;

Abakshikha – Bolsheukovskiy district, 39 km NW of Bolshiye Uki, Abakshikha boundary, 57°16'18.59"N, 72°19'55.78"E;

Alabota – Russko-Polyansky district, 1,5 km N of Alabota vill., near lake Kumdykol', 53°58'28.24"N, 73°45'1.22"E;

Alekseevskoye boundary – Maryanovskiy district, Alekseevskoye boundary, 54°56'43.76" N, 72°41'35.17"E;

Andreevka – Omsky district, Andreevka village vicinities, 55°5'38.13"N 73°37'16.14"E;

Artyn – Muromtsevskiy district, Artyn vill., 56°9'10.98"N, 74°45'27.97"E;

Atak – Tarsky district, Atak village vicinities, 56°48'24"N, 74°38'36"E;

Atmas – Cherlacksky district, 2 km of Malyi Atmas vill., river Irtysh, 54°0'48.74"N, 74°56'39.91"E; fig. 2.

Basly – Bolsheukovsky district, 15 km SE of Basly vill., 56°56'42"N, 72°57'24"E;

Belogrivka – Bolsheukovsky district, Belogrivka vill., 56°37'36.86"N, 72°50'33.78"E;

Bolshiye Uki – Bolsheukovsky district, Bolshiye Uki vill., 56°55'37"N, 72°37'37"E;

Bolshoi Atmas – Cherlacksky district, 3,5 km N of Bolshoi Atmas vill., 54°6'22.15"N, 74°56'28.85"E;

Buzan – Russko-Polyansky district, 2 km SE of Buzan vill., 53°54'40"N, 73°57'31"E; fig. 3.

Cherlack – Cherlacksky district, Cherlack vill., 54°9'1.89"N, 74°48'54.39"E;

Cherlack station – Cherlacksky district, Cherlack rail station, 53°52'59.37"N, 75°5'44.21"E;

Davydovka – Omsky district, 2 km N of Davydovka vill., 55°11'14"N, 73°29'47"E;

Ekaterininskoye – Tarsky district, Ekaterininskoye vill., 56°52'59.44"N, 74°36'40.34"E;

Elita – Omsk City, «Elita» gardens, 55°1'48.80"N, 73°32'54.30"E;

Ermak – Novovarshevsky district, Ermak vill., 53°56'33.01"N, 75°0'50.49"E;

Forpost – Bolsheukovsky district, Forpost vill., 56°47'14.97"N, 72°9'50.07"E;

Gulyai Pole – Krutinsky district, 44 km NW of Krutinka vill., 5 km SW of Gulyai Pole vill., 56°13'30.08"N, 70°53'44.58"E;

Isakovka – Gorkovsky district, Isakovka vill. vicinities, 55°44'47.60"N, 74°25'28.07"E;

Isilkul' – Isil'kul'sky district, Isil'kul' town, 54°54'52.55"N, 71°15'46.01"E;

Kaingash – Tevriszsky district, Kaingash boundary, 57°32'58.67"N, 72°13'14.90"E;

Kalmatskoye – Nazyvaevsky district, 3 km W of Kalmatskoye vill., near lake Beloye, 55°27'41.54"N, 70°48'17.99"E;

Kamyshino – Okoneshnikovsky district, 4 km NW of Kamyshino vill., 54°43'35.33"N, 74°50'7.52"E;

Khlebodarovka – Russko-Polyansky district, 8 km SW of Khlebodarovka vill., river Tleusai, 53°42'7.53"N, 73°25'11.71"E;

Knyazevo – Nazyvaevsky district, Knyazevo vill., 55°20'35.76"N, 70°59'30.04"E;

Kormilovka – Kormilovsky district, Kormilovka vill., 55°0'17.54"N, 74°5'33.67"E;

Krasnoyarka – Omsky district, Krasnoyarka vill., 55°20'0.22"N, 73°5'33.67"E;

Krasnyi Oktyabr' – Cherlacksky district, Krasnyi Oktyabr' village vicinities, 54°06'59"N, 75°01'01"E;

Leninsk – Okoneshnikovsky district, 4 km S of Leninsk vill., 54°29'53.56"N, 75°29'21.15"E;

Linevo – Muromtsevsky district, 6,5 km S of Kondratyevoye vill., near lake Linevo, 56°24'29.38"N, 75°37'7.47"E;

Listvyagi – Bolsheukovsky district, Listvyagi vill., 57°14'11.26"N, 71°54'52.42"E;

Luzino – Omsky district, Luzino village vicinities, 54°56'57.29"N, 73° 2'8.82"E;
Lyubinka – Bolsheukovsky district, Lyubinka boundary, 57°3'17.10"N, 72°42'35.30"E;

Maiskiy – Moskalensky district, 3,5 km NNW of Maiskiy vill., 55°8'37.13"N, 71°43'48.28"E;

Maryikha – Bolsheukovsky district, Maryikha boundary, 56°59'28.30"N, 72°59'22.00"E;

Mezhdurechye – Tarsky district, Mezhdurechye vill., 56°48'4.31"N, 74°36'31.78"E;

Muromtsevo – Muromtsevsky district, Muromtsevo vill. vicinities, river Tara, 56°21'55.20"N, 75°16'23.86"E;

Novovarshavka – Novovarshavsky district, 3 km E of Novovarshavka vill., Irtysh river, 54°10'0.80"N, 74°45'24.81"E;

Novyi Koshkul' – Tyukalinsky district, 0,5 km N of Novyi Koshkul', 56°0'11.34"N, 72°20'42.12"E;

Orekhovo – Ust'-Ishimsky district, 2 km NE of Orekhovo vill., 57°28'3.37"N, 70°53'3.34"E;

Osokino – Kalachinsky district, Osokino vill., 54°53'2.48"N, 74°36'37.01"E;

Partsyezd – Omsky district, XVIII Partsyezd village vicinities, 55°6'48.24"N, 73°38'30.30"E;

Petropavlovka – Muromtsevsky district, Petropavlovka village vicinities, 56°24'46"N, 75°16'44"E; fig. 1.

Podgorodka – Omsky district, Podgorodka village vicinities, 55°8'10.38"N, 73°30'42.90"E;

Politotdel – Lyubinsky district, 2 km W of Politotdel vill., 55°12'36.59"N, 73°7'25.20"E;

Rozovka – Russko-Polyansky district, Rozovka village vicinities, 53°51'4.26"N, 74°2'25.11"E;

Ryamovka – Bolshrechensky district, Ryamovka village vicinities, sphagnum bog, 55°59'22.5"N 74°21'21.8"E;

Russkaya Polyana – Russko-Polyansky district, Russkaya Polyana vill., park "Yubileinyi", 53°46'29.60"N, 73°51'53.91"E;

Samsonovo – Tarsky district, 4 km N of Samsonovo vill., 57°0'47.38"N, 74°19'49.44"E;

Sedelnikovo – Sedelnikovsky district, 2 km N of Sedelnikovo vill., 56°58'22.33"N, 75°17'13.09"E;

Slobodchiki – Ust'-Ishimsky district, Slobodchiki vill., 57°30'6.19"N, 70°56'2.73"E;

Solyanoye – Cherlacksky district, Solyanoye village vicinities, 54°21'4.40"N, 74°38'2.06"E;

Tevriz – Tevrizsky district, Tevriz village vicinities, 57°30'48.17"N, 72°23'11.88"E;

Timshinyakovo – Tarsky district, 0,5 km N of Timshinyakovo vill., 56°57'8.97"N, 74°25'49.51"E;

Tshaunino – Bolsheukovsky district, Tshaunino vill., 57° 8'46.44"N, 73° 5'0.05"E;
Ul'zhai – Cherlacksy district, 6 km SE of Nikolaevka vill., lake Ul'zhai, 54°13'48.02"N, 75° 6'51.61"E;

Ust`-Tava – Bolsheukovsky district, 9 km W of Listvyagi vill., Ust`-Tava boundary, 57°14'56.45"N, 71°44'35.98"E;

Vasiss – Tarsky district, Vasiss vill., 57°21'32.47"N, 74°44'15.50"E;

Victory Park – Omsk City, Kirovsky district, Victory Park, 54°58'3.21"N, 73°22'0.03"E;

Yakovlevka – Bolsheukovsky district, 28 km NW of Bolshiye Uki vill., Yakovlevka boundary, river Tevriz, 57°10'38.79"N, 72°25'16.34"E.

The nomenclature and order of taxa is given according to M.L. Danilevsky (Danilevsky 2021) with some changes according to A.I. Cherepanov (Cherepanov 1979, 1981, 1982, 1983, 1984, 1985) and the Catalog of the Palearctic Coleoptera (Danilevsky 2020).

Figure 1. Pine forest in Muromtsevsky district, Petropavlovka village (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

Figure 2. Steppe slopes near river Irtysh in Cherlacksy district, 2 km N of Malyi Atmos vill (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

Figure 3. Steppe in Russko-Polyansky district, 2 km SE of Buzan village (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

Results

Checklist:

Familia: CERAMBYCIDAE

Subfamilia: LEPTURINAE

Tribus: RHAGIINI

1. **Rhagium mordax* (De Geer, 1775)

Material examined. 1♂, 2♀, Listvyagi, 2006, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Listvyagi, 9.VII.2008, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 1♀, Yakovlevka, 15.VI.2019, 27.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 3♂, Abakshikha, 27.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2 spm., Abakshikha, 21-22.V.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2♂, Maryikha, 17.VI.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2♂, Bolshiye Uki, 14.VI.2020, 20-22.VI.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2♂, 4♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♀, Petropavlovka, 22.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Petropavlovka, 29.V.2008, S.A. Knyazev (OGKM); 1♂, Ryamovka, 26.V.2022, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS).

2. **Rhagium inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 4)

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 5♂, 3♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, 9.VII.2007, 11.VII.2008, 12.VI.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 9.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 10.VI.2013, 18.VI.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♀, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 3♂, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Sedelnikovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Krasnoyarka, 11.VII.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Podgorodka, 8.XI.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

3. **Pachyta quadrimaculata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. 1 spm., Ust'-Tava, 24.VIII.2018, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 4♂, 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♀, Timshinyakovo, 8.VII.2020, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♀, Atak, 6.VII.2008, V.G. Zaulitskaya (OGKM); 1♀, Petropavlovka, 11.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Petropavlovka, 10.VII.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

4. **Evodinellus borealis* (Gyllenhal, 1827)

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, no date, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO).

5. *Toxotus quercus* (Götz, 1783)

Lavrov, 1927: 86

Remark. No modern material presented. Erroneous determination possible.

6. *Brachyta interrogationis* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 5)

Lavrov, 1927: 86 (*Evodinus (Brachyta) interrogationis* L.); Tshernyshev, Dubatolov, 2005: 45, Omsk.

Material examined. 2♂, 1♀, Orekhovo, 21.VI.2008, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1 spm., Listvyagi, 18.VI.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 2♂, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, 1♀, Abakshikha, 17.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 3♂, 2♀, Yakovlevka, 15.VI.2019, 8.VII.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, 29.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 3 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 10.VI.2013, 20.VI.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 10.VI.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 2 spm., Basly, 10.VI.2010, 30.VII.2010, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 2♂, 2♀, Basly, 7.VII.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♀, Atak, VI.1996, students of Omsk State pedagogical university (OGKM); 7♀, Sedelnikovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Petropavlovka, 6.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Artyn, 11.VI.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, 1♀, Gulyai Pole, 7-8.VI.2016, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 6♂, 6♀, Knyazevo, 22.VI.1996, 1.V.1996, 7.VI.1983, 26.VI.1996, 8.VIII.1996, 24.VI.2010, 4.VI.1983, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 1♀, Davydovka, 17.VI.2000, 30.VI.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 4♂, 5♀, Davydovka, 23.VI.2009, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 3♂, Podgorodka, 31.V.2001, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Omsk vic., on the flowers of Sorbus, 14.VI.1984, A.V. Barkalov (ISEA); 1♀, Partseyezd, 18.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

7. *Brachyta variabilis* (Gebler, 1817)

Lavrov, 1927: 86 (*Evodinus (Brachyta) variabilis* Gebl.)

Material examined. 2♀, Sedelnikovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 5♂, Knyazevo, 14.V.1982, 5.V.1983, 17.V.1982, 2.V.1983, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

8. **Carilia virginea* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. 1♂, Tevriz, 9.VII.2002, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 4♂, 1♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1 spm., Listvyagi, 18.VI.2007,

V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 15.VIII.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, 1♀, Artyn, 11.VI.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

9. **Euracmaeops smaragdulus* (Fabricius, 1793)

Material examined. 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 17.VI.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO).

10. *Gnathacmaeops pratensis* (Linnaeus, 1784)

Lavrov, 1927: 86 (*Acmaeops pratensis* Laich.)

Material examined. 1 spm., Listvyagi, no date, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 20.VI.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 15.VI.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 18.VI.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 22.VI.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1 spm., Krasnoyarka, 30.VI.1984, K.B. Ponomarev (VTO).

11. **Dinoptera collaris* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. 1 spm., Forpost, 30.VI.2017, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, Knyazev, 24.VI.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Krasnoyarka, 28.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Luzino, 23.VI.1997, T.Ф. Кошелева (OGKM); 1 spm., Omsk, 16.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (photo); 1♂, Partsyezd, 18.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Rozovka, 21.VI.2007, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Russkaya Polyana, 18.VI.2007, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM).

Tribus: LEPTURINI

12. **Nivellia sanguinosa* (Gyllenhal, 1827)

Material examined. 1♂, Abakshikha, 3.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA).

13. *Pseudovadonia livida* (Fabricius, 1777)

Lavrov, 1927: 86 (*Grammoptera livida* F.)

Material examined. 1♂, 2♀, Podgorodka, 24.VI.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 3♂, Luzino, 23.VI.1997, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Omsk, 15.VII.1996, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Omsk, 28.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2 spm., Victory Park, 18.VII.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA).

14. *Stictoleptura rubra* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 86 (*Leptura rubra* L.)

Material examined. 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 7.VIII.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 2♂, Bolshiye Uki, 4.VII.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 3♀, Basly, 30.VII.2010, 17.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1 spm., Basly, 17.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, 1♀, Atak, 8.VII.2008, V.G. Zaulitskaya (OGKM); 1♂, Petropavlovka, 10.VII.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Petropavlovka, 11.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Linevo, 13.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM).

15. **Anoplodera sanguinolenta* (Linnaeus, 1760)

Material examined. 1 ♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1 ♂, Abakshikha, 3.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 15.VIII.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1 spm., Samsonovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (ISEA); 1 ♀, Petropavlovka, 11.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM).

16. **Anastrangalia sequensi* (Reitter, 1898)

Material examined. 2 ♂, 2 ♀, Tevriz, 9-11.VII.2002, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1 ♂, 3 ♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 13 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 21.VI.2009, 24.VI.2019, 20.VI.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 7 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 11.VI.2016, 21.VI.2016, 13.VI.2016, 29-30.V.2016, 10.VI.2013, 30.VII.2010 V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1 ♂, Belogrivka, 16.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1 ♂, Basly, 7.VII.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1 spm., Basly, 30.VII.2010, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1 ♂, Atak, 8.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 4 ♀, Petropavlovka, 10.VII.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 5 ♀, Gulyai Pole, 19.VI.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 ♂, Knyazev, 26.VI.1997, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 ♂, Isakovka, 12.VII.1995, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1 ♂, Alekseevskoye boundary, 18.VII.2001, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2 ♂, Politotdel, 23.VI.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2 ♂, Krasnoyarka, 22.VI.2001, 26.VI.1997, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Podgorodka, 24.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Davydovka, 14.VI.2009, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Partseyzd, 18.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (SKSS);

17. *Lepturobosca virens* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 6)

Lavrov, 1927: 86 (*Leptura virens* L.). Omsk, Tara.

Material examined. 2 ♂, Tevriz, 9-11.VII.2002, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 3 ♂, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 6 ♂, 4 ♀, Basly, 7.VII.2019, 15.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1 spm., Basly, 15.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1 ♂, Timshinyakovo, 8.VII.2020, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1 ♂, Atak, VI.1996, students of Omsk State pedagogical university (OGKM); 1 ♂, Ekaterininskoye, 8.VII.1998, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1 ♀, Petropavlovka, 11.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 9 ♂, Petropavlovka, 10.VII.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, Gulyai Pole, 19.VI.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 ♀, Krasnoyarka, 26.VI.1995, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 ♂, Davydovka, 30.VI.2017, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 spm., Podgorodka, 24.VI.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1 ♂, Partseyzd, 18.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

18. **Judolia sexmaculata* Linnaeus, 1758

Material examined. 1 ♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 2 spm., Listvyagi, 24.VI.2017, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1 spm., Maiskyi, 30.VI.2021, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

19. **Pachytodes erraticus* (Dalman, 1817) (Fig. 7)

Material examined. 1♀, Listvyagi, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♀, Artyn, 11.VI.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 4♂, Knyazev, 26.VI.1982, 9.VIII.1994, 8.VII.1988, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂7♀, Kalmatskoye, 7.VII.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Isakovka, 12.VII.1995, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2♀, 624 km., 9.VII.1997, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, Alekseevskoye boundary, 11.VII.2001, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2♂, 2♀, Krasnoyarka, 29-30.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Podgorodka, 24.VI.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 2♂, 2♀, Andreevka, VI.2020, 24.VI.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, 2♀, Partsyezd, 18.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, 1♀, Osokino, 30.VIII.2010, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM).

20. *Pachytodes cerambyciformis* (Schrank, 1781)

Lavrov, 1927: 86 (*Pachyta cerambyciformis* Schr.)

Remark. No modern materials from Omsk Region. Lavrov's identification is probably erroneous, since the general distribution of the species in Russia includes only the European part (Danilevsky, 2021).

21. **Oedecnema gebleri* Ganglbauer, 1889 =*dubia* (Fabricius, 1781) (Fig. 8)

Material examined. 2♂, 1♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1 spm., Abakshikha, 3.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 3 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 10.VI.2013, 11.VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 20.VI.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 3 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 15.VI.2015, 29-30.V.2016, 11.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Atak, 10.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Atak, VI.1996, students of Omsk State pedagogical university (OGKM); 1♀, Gulyai Pole, 19.VI.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

22. **Leptura thoracica* (Creutzer, 1799)

Material examined. 1♀, Listvyagi, 21.VII.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♀, Yakovlevka, 8.VII.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, 1♀, Forpost, 30.VI.2017, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, 14.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 4♂, 3♀, Knyazev, 26.VI.1996, 26.VI.1981, 8.VII.1988, 30.VI.1982, 8.VII.1995, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Knyazev, 30.VI.1982, K.B. Ponomarev (OGKM); 1♀, Knyazev, 30.VI.1982, K.B. Ponomarev (ISEA); 1♂, 2♀, Podgorodka, 24.VI.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, 2♀, Davydovka, 4.VII.2010, 17.VI.2001, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Omsk, territory of Omsk State Agrarian University, 25.VI.2021, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

23. *Leptura quadrifasciata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 86 (*Strangalia quadrifasciata* L.). Omsk.

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Slobodchiki, 22.VI.2008, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Tevriz, Irtysh river floodplain, 8.VII.2002, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂2♀, Tevriz, 9,11.VII.2002, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Kaingash, 10.VII.2002, T.F.

Kosheleva (OGKM); 1 spm., Listvyagi, no date, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2♂, 3♀, Listvyagi, VI-VII.2005, V-VI.2006, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Abakshikha, 17.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2♂, 3♀, Yakovlevka, 8.VII.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 10.VIII.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 4♂, 2♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 10.VIII.2013, 10.VII.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2♂, 2♀, Bolshiye Uki, 1.VII.2007, 27.VI.2011, 5.VII.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 3♂, Basly, 7.VII.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♀, Samsonovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 2♀, Atak, VI.1996, 20-26.VII.1997, students of Omsk State pedagogical university (OGKM); 1♂, Muromtsevo, 12.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Gulyai Pole, 19.VI.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 1♀, Kalmatskoye, 7.VII.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 4♂, 3♀, Knyazevo, 23.VII.1992, 2.VII.1982, 8.VII.1988, 7.VII.1994, 8.VI.1988, 7.VII.1998, 21.VI.2016, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Maiskiy, 30.VI.2021, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 624 km., 7.VII.1997, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Alekseevskoye boundary, 18.VII.2001, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Isakovka, 12.VII.1995, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, 3♀, Krasnoyarka, 29-30.VI.1994, 26.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 3♀, Davydovka, 4.VII.2010, 30.VI.2017, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 2♀, Partsyезд, 18.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

24. **Leptura annularis* Fabricius, 1801 (Fig. 9)

Material examined. 3♂, 2♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Abakshikha, 17.VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, Yakovlevka, 8.VII.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♀, Yakovlevka, 23.VII.2017, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, 24.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 3♂, 3♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, 19.VI.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♀, Lyubinka, 24.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 7♂, 1♀, Basly, 7.VII.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♀, Sedelnikovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

25. **Leptura aethiops* (Poda, 1761) Fig. 10.

Material examined. 1♂, Tevriz, 11.VII.2002, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1 spm., Listvyagi, 6.VII.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 25.VI.2015, 23.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1 spm., Basly, 30.VII.2010, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2♀, Samsonovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Petropavlovka, 11.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Krasnoyarka, 30.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

26. *Leptura nigripes* (De Geer, 1775) (Fig. 11)

Lavrov, 1927: 86

Material examined. 1 spm., Listvyagi, 1.VII.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 5♂, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Listvyagi, 9.VII.2008, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Abakshikha, 17.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 4♂, 2♀, Yakovlevka, 8.VII.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2♂, Bolshiye Uki,

7.VII.2016, 24.VI.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 5♂, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 6 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 15.VI.2015, 21.VI.2016, 11.VI.2016, 15.VIII.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 1.VII.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 2♂, 3♀, Basly, 7.VII.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2 spm., Basly, 30.VII.2010, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Ekaterininskoye, 8.VII.1998, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Atak, 20-26.VI.1997, students of Omsk State pedagogical university, (OGKM); 1♀, Sedelnikovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 3♂, 2♀, Gulyai Pole, 19.VI.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Gulyai Pole, 7-8.VI.2016, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Knyazevo, 30.VI.1991, K.B. Ponomarev (OGKM); 8♂, 13♀, Knyazevo, 22.VI.1996, 30.VI.1982, 23.VI.2010, 23.VII.1992, 30.VI.1997, 8.VII.1988, 16.VII.2011, 26.VI.1997, 25.VI.1981, 26.VII.1981, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Kalmatskoye, 7.VII.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Isakovka, 12.VII.1995, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2♂, 1♀, Krasnoyarka, 30.VI.1994, 16.VI.2012, 29.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, 2♀, Davydovka, 7.VIII.2009, 4.VII.2010, 30.VI.2017, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, 2♀, Partsyezd, 26.VI.2021, 18.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♀, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 2.VII.2008, S.A. Knyazev (OGKM); 1♂, Cherlack station, 1.VI.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

27. **Strangalia attenuata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. 2♂, Petropavlovka, 11.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Isakovka, 12.VII.1995, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 4♂, Krasnoyarka, 27.VI.1994, 19.VII.1998, 23.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 6♂, 1♀, Davydovka, 4.VII.2010, 30.VI.2017, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

28. *Stenurella bifasciata* (Müller, 1776)

Lavrov, 1927: 86 (*Strangalia bifasciata* Müll.)

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Listvyagi, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 2♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♂, 1♀, Timshinyakovo, 8.VII.2020, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Petropavlovka, 10.VII.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 2♀, Knyazevo, 26.VI.1981, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, 624 km., 19.VII.1996, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, 1♀, Krasnoyarka, 29-30.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 spm., Victory Park, 28.VII.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, Andreevka, VI.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 3♀, Leninsk, 1.VII.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, Atmos, 5.VII.2011, 7.VII.2011, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

29. **Stenurella melanura* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Tevriz, 9-11.VII.2002, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Ekaterininskoye, 8.VII.1998, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Mezhdurechye, 7-8.VI.2009, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2♂, 1♀, Petropavlovka, 11.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Linevo, 13.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1 spm., Victory Park, 18.VII.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA).

Subfamilia: NECYDALINAE

Tribus: NECYDALINI

30. *Necydalis major* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 86

Material examined. 1♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 2♂, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 1.VIII.2010, 6.VIII.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1 spm., Basly, 17.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Knyazevo, 29.VI.1991, K.B. Ponomarev (OGKM); 1♂, 5♀, Knyazevo, 15.VI.1988, 23.VI.1981, 7.VII.1998, 10.VI.1992, 16.VII.2011, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Maiskiy, 3.VII.2021, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, 624 km, 10.VII.1998, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Podgorodka, 24.VI.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Davydovka, 4.VII.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 1990, O.N. Kholodov (OKO).

Subfamilia: SPONDYLIDINAE

Tribus: ASEMINI

31. *Asemum striatum* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 84. Omsk.

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, 26.VI.2017, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2♂, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 4♂, Bolshiye Uki, 12.VI.2011, 9.VII.2007, 11.VII.2008, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO).

32. *Arhopalus rusticus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 12)Lavrov, 1927: 84 (*Criocephalus rusticus*, L.). Podgorodka, Omsk.

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, 1♀, Listvyagi, 9.VI.2008, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 26.VII.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, 3♀, Bolshiye Uki, 14.VII.2018, at light, 18.VI.2020, 16.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, 3♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♀, Samsonovo, 20-21.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS); 1 spm., Petropavlovka, 24.VII.2010, S.A. Knyazev (photo); 1♂, Petropavlovka, at light, 14-15.VII.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 4♀, Krasnoyarsk, at light, 24.VI.2012, 22.VI.2012, 25.VI.2011, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Cherlack, at light, 10.VII.2016, A.A. Sal'nik (ASO).

Tribus: TETROPIINI

33. *Tetropium castaneum* (Linnaeus, 1758)Lavrov, 1927: 84 (*Tetropium luridum*, L.)

Material examined. 2♂, Listvyagi, V.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 29-30.V.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2♀, Bolshiye Uki,

VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 4 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 29-30.V.2016, 24-27.V.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2♀, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2♂, 3♀, Victory Park, 16.VI.1996, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Omsk, V.1996, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1 spm., Omsk vicinities, on Taraxacum flowers, 14.VI.1984, A.V. Barkalov (ISEA).

Tribus: SPONDYLYDINI

34. **Spondilis buprestoides* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 13)

Material examined. 1♂, Atak, 6.VII.2008, V.G. Zaulitskaya (OGKM); 1 spm., Petropavlovka, 24.VII.2010, at light, S.A. Knyazev (photo).

Subfamilia: CERAMBYCINAE

Tribus: HESPEROPHANINI

35. **Trichoferus campestris* (Faldermann, 1835)

Material examined. 4♂, 3♀, Achair, ex larvae from Padus log, 3.VI.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

Tribus: PURPURICENINI

36. *Purpuricenus globulicollis* Mulsant, 1839 (Fig. 14)

Knyazev et al., 2015: 64-65 (*Purpuricenus kaehleri* Linnaeus 1758).

Material examined. 1♂, Knyazev, 23.VI.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Partsyezd, 26.VI.2021, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 17.VII.2009, O.N. Kholodov (OGKM).

37. **Anoplistes halodendri* (Pallas, 1773)

Material examined. 3♂, Khlebodarovka, 9.VI.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Ermak, 2.VI.2022, A.A. Sal'nik (ASO).

Tribus: CALLICHROMATINI

38. *Aromia moschata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 84. Omsk.

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, 10.VII.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, Listvyagi, 18.VII.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Listvyagi, 16.VII.2004, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 15.VIII.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 2 spm., Basly, 14.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, 2♀, Knyazev, 23.VII.1992, 16.VII.2011, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

Tribus: OBRIINI

39. **Obrium cantharinum* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Material examined. 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 14.VII.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, 2♀, Knyazevo, 26.VI.1997, 3.VII.1992, 26.VI.1997, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Krasnoyarka, 16.VI.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 spm., Omsk, 6.VII.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO).

Tribus: MOLORCHINI

40. **Molorchus minor* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, on Sorbus inflorescence, 24.VI.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 2♂, 2♀, Bolshiye Uki, on Sorbus inflorescence, 24.VI.2018, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 19.VI.2014, 23.VI.2018, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO).

Tribus: CALLIDIINI

41. **Semanotus undatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 15)

Material examined. 1 spm., Listvyagi, 11.V.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 21.VI.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 58 spm., Podgorodka, ex larva, from Picea log, 21-30.I.2022, S.M. Saikina, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS, OGKM, KPO).

42. **Palaeocallidium coriaceum* Paykull, 1800

Material examined. 2♂, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM).

43. **Callidium chlorizans* (Solsky, 1871)

Material examined. 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, in the house, 22.III.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO).

44. **Callidium violaceum* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Maryikha, 17.VI.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 3♂, 3♀, Bolshiye Uki, 20-22.VI.2019, 24.VI.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 5♂, 3♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 24-27.V.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Lyubinka, 24.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, 1♀, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2♂, 3♀, Knyazevo, 8.VII.1983, 2.VI.1982, 1.VI.1996, 30.VI.1981, 3.VI.2016, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Victory Park, 25.V.1997, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Cherlack, 23.V.2017, A.A. Sal`nik (ASO); 1♂, 1♀, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, 26.V.2022, O.N. Kholodov (SKSS).

45. **Callidium aeneum* (De Geer, 1775)

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Listvyagi, V.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, in the house, 22.III.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Knyazevo, 9.VI.2007, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

Tribus: CLYTINI

46. *Echinocerus floralis* (Pallas, 1773) (Fig. 16)

Lavrov, 1927: 84 (*Clytus (Plaqionotus) floralis* Pall.)

Material examined. 1♂, Krasnoyarka, 27.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Kormilovka, 26.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 4♂, Elita, 24.VI.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

47. **Chlorophorus figuratus* (Scopoli, 1763)

Material examined. 3♂, 1♀, Krasnoyarka, 29-30.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

48. *Rhaphuma gracilipes* (Faldermann, 1835)

Lavrov, 1927: 85 (*Clytus (Chlorophorus) gracilipes* Fald.). Omsk.

Material examined. 1 spm., Abakshikha, 23.VI.2017, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 11.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1 spm., Knyazevo, 10.VI.1982, K.B. Ponomarev (ISEA).

49. *Xylotrechus ibex* (Gebler, 1825)

Lavrov, 1927: 85 (*Clytus (Xylotrechus) ibex* Gebl.). Omsk.

Material examined. 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 14.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, 12.VI.2017, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♀, Tshaunino, 8.VII.2018, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, 3♀, Knyazevo, 30.VI.1982, 16.VI.1991, 8.VIII.1992, 8.VII.1996, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

50. *Xylotrechus hircus* (Gebler, 1825)

Lavrov, 1927: 85 (*Clytus (Xylotrechus) hircus* Gebl.). Omsk.

Material examined. 1♂, 4♀, Knyazevo, 8.VIII.1996, 21.VI.1981, 8.VII.1996, 16.VI.1983, 8.VII.1995, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Podgorodka, 8.VI.1998, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

51. *Xylotrechus rusticus* (Linnaeus, 1758) Fig. 17.

Lavrov, 1927: 84. Podgorodka.

Material examined. 1♂, Slobodchiki, 22.VI.2008, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2♀, Listvyagi, 2006, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 24-27.V.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 3 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 24-27.V.2017, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 2♂1♀, Maryikha, 17.VI.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Atak, VI.1998, students of Omsk State pedagogical university (OGKM); 6♂, 7♀, Knyazevo, 2.V.1982,

22.VI.2010, 10.VIII.1990, 18.VI.1983, 8.VII.1996, 21.VI.1981, 23.VI.1983, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Knyazevo, 19.VI.1991, K.B. Ponomarev (OGKM); 1 spm., Krasnoyarsk, 16.VI.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (ISEA); 2♂, 1♀, Davydovka, 9.VI.2004, 16.VI.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Omsk, 23.V.2021, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Partsyezd, 21-30.I.2022, ex larva, from Birch log, S.M. Saikina, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS); 2♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 14.VI.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 1.VII.2022, O.N. Kholodov (SKSS).

52. **Cyrtoclytus capra* (German, 1824)

Material examined. 1 spm., Listvyagi, VI.2005, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2♂, 1♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♀, Yakovlevka, 8.VII.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Yakovlevka, 23.VII.2017, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, Bolshiye Uki, 29.VI.2009, 14.VII.2018, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2♀, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 25.VI.2015, 29.VI.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 23.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, Lyubinka, 24.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Basly, 7.VII.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 6♂, 2♀, Knyazevo, 30.VI.1982, 2.VII.1992, 23.VI.2010, 21.VI.2016, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, 3♀, Krasnoyarsk, 30.VI.1994, 16.VI.2012, 29.VI.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 3♂, Davydovka, 20.VI.2000, 30.VI.2017, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Andreevka, VI.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Elita, 24.VI.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

53. **Clytus arietoides* Reitter, 1899

Material examined. 1♀, Tshaunino, 8.VII.2018, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM).

Subfamilia: LAMIINAE

Tribus: MESOSINI

54. *Mesosa myops* (Dalman, 1817)

Lavrov, 1927: 85 (*Mesosa* (= *Haplocnemia*) *myops* Dalm.). Podgorodka, Omsk.

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1 spm., Listvyagi, 11.VI.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 29-30.V.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 18.VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, Lyubinka, 24.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, 1♀, Knyazevo, 10.VI.1983, 25.V.1993, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 6♂, 1♀, Knyazevo, 23.V.1983, K.B. Ponomarev (OGKM); 1♂, 3♀, Davydovka, 16.VI.2010, 19.VII.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Andreevka, 6.VI.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, 1♀, Cherlack, 3.VII.2016, 22.V.2016, A.A. Sal`nik (ASO).

Tribus: MONOCHAMINI

55. **Monochamus impluviatus* (Motschulsky, 1859)

Material examined. 2♂, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 2♂, Bolshiye Uki, 11.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Knyazevo, 26.VII.1992, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Krasnoyarka, 19.VII.1998, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂ Victory Park 16.VI.1996, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

56. **Monochamus galloprovincialis* (Olivier, 1800)

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Yakovlevka, 8.VII.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 18.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 5♂, 2♀, Petropavlovka, 14-16.VII.2021, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS); 1♂, Muromtsevo, 10.VII.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Knyazevo, 15.VIII.1991, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Novyi Koshkul', 24.VI.2019, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Atmas, 21.VI.2019, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Atmas, 14-15.VII.2020, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS).

57. **Monochamus urussovi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806)

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 2♀, Bolshiye Uki, 29.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 9.VII.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 31.VII.2018, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO) 1♂, Vasiss, 22.VII.1972, P. Chernousov (KPO); 1♀, Knyazevo, 22.VII.1988, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

58. *Monochamus sutor* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 85. Omsk.

Material examined. 4♂, 1♀ Listvyagi, 2006, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♀, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 3♂, Bolshiye Uki, 11.VI.2016, 24.VI.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 4 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 29-30.V.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Samsonovo, 07.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Vasiss, 24.VII.1972, V. Aleshin (KPO); 1♂, Ekaterininskoye, 8.VII.1998, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Atak, 7.VII.2007, V.G. Zaulitskaya (OGKM); 1♂, Atak, VI.1996, students of Omsk State pedagogical university, (OGKM); 1♂, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Knyazevo, 26.VII.1992, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Knyazevo, 15.VIII.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Omsk, VI.1995, S.D. Averbukh (OGKM); 1♂, Cherlack, 12.V.2016, A.A. Sal`nik (ASO).

59. *Monochamus saltuarius* Gebler, 1830

Lavrov, 1927: 85

Remark. No modern materials from the territory of Omsk Region.

Tribus: LAMIINI

60. *Lamia textor* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 85. Omsk, Podgorodka.

Material examined. 1♀, Orekhovo, 21.VI.2008, S.A. Knyazev (KPO); 1♀, Orekhovo, 21.VI.2008, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 2.VI.2011, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 24.VI.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Basly, 15.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, 1♀, Davydovka, 4.VII.2010, 19.VII.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

Tribus: DORCADIONINI

61. *Politorcadion politum* (Dalman, 1823) ssp. *knyazevi* Danilevsky 2020 (Fig. 18)

Danilevsky, 2020: 103-111. Buzan.

Material examined. 2♂, Buzan, PARATYPUS, 22.IV.2020, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS); 12♂, 3♀, Buzan, 26.IV.2020, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS); 1♂, Buzan, 5.V.2021, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Ermak, 4.V.2020, A.A. Sal`nik (ASO); 7♂, Ermak, 23.IV.2016, 3.IV.2017, 28.IV.2017, A.A. Sal`nik (KPO); 1♂, 1♀, Ermak, 9.V.2018, A.A. Sal`nik (SKSS); 1♂, Ermak, 28.IV.2017, A.A. Sal`nik (VTO).

62. *Eodorcadion carinatum* (Fabricius, 1781)

Lavrov, 1927: 85 (*Neodorcadion involvens* Fisch.)

Material examined. 1♀, Atak, VI.1998, students of Omsk State pedagogical university (OGKM); 3♂, Krasnoyarka, 24.VII.2012, 1.VII.1994, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Politotdel, 23.VI.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Omsk, Troitskoye (KPO); 1♂, Partsyezd, 26.VI.2021, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 2 spm., Krasnyi Oktyabr`, 1990, O.N. Kholodov (visual registration); 1♀, Ermak, 9.VII.2017, A.A. Sal`nik (ASO).

Tribus: APODASYINI

63. *Anaesthesia testacea* (Fabricius, 1781)

Lavrov, 1927: 86. Omsk.

Remark. No modern materials from the territory of Omsk Region.

Tribus: POGONOCHEININI

64. *Pogonocherus fasciculatus* (De Geer, 1775)

Lavrov, 1927: 85

Material examined. 1♀, Listvyagi, 9.VII.2008, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, 29.VI.2011, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 11.V.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♀, Knyazevo, 3.V.1988, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂,

Cherlack, 23.IV.2016, A.A. Sal'nik (ASO); 1♂, Cherlack station, 1.VI.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

Tribus: ACANTHODERINI

65. *Aegomorphus clavipes* (Schorank, 1781)

Lavrov, 1927: 99

Material examined. 4♂, 1♀, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 7 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 11.VI.2016, 24.VI.2019, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 3 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 2.VI.2015, 11.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Samsonovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Timshinyakovo, 8.VII.2020, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♀, Atak, 20-26.VI.1997, students of Omsk State pedagogical university (OGKM); 8♂, 5♀, Knyazevo, 8.VII.1995, 1.VIII.1992, 22.VI.2010, 22.VII.1988, 8.VII.1988, 17.VIII.1992, 19.VII.1982, 10.VI.1983, 31.VI.1982, 17.IV.1983, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Knyazevo, 23.V.1983, K.B. Ponomarev (OGKM); 1♀, Davydovka, 16.VI.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, Andreevka, 9.VI.2020, 13.VI.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Elita, 20.V.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♀, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 6.VI.2009, O.N. Kholodov (OGKM); 1♀, Cherlack station, 1.VI.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

Tribus: ACANTHOCININI

66. *Acanthocinus griseus* (Fabricius, 1793)

Lavrov, 1927: 85. Omsk.

Material examined. 1♀, Listvyagi, 9.VII.2008, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 8.VI.2009, 7.VI.2011, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 6♂, 4♀, Bolshiye Uki, 18.VI.2021, 12.VI.2017, 19.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, 29.VI.2011, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♀, Knyazevo, 11.VI.1995, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Atmos, 27.VI.2021, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

67. **Acanthocinus carinulatus* (Gebler, 1883)

Material examined. 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 29.VI.2011, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♀, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Knyazevo, 15.VIII.1996. K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

68. *Acanthocinus aedilis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 85 (*Astynomus* (= *Acanthocinus*) *aedilis* L.). Omsk.

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Listvyagi, 10.VII.2008, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Abakshikha, 17.VI.2021, 3♂, 3♀, Bolshiye Uki, 18.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 7♂, 2♀, Bolshiye Uki, 10.VII.2008, 11.VII.2008, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♀, Timshinya-

kovo, 27.IV.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♀, Atak, 8.VII.2007, V.G. Zaulitskaya (OGKM); 1♂, Petropavlovka, 26.V.2009, V.V. Rogalev (ISEA).

Tribus: TETROPINI

69. *Tetrops praeustus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 85 (*Tetrops praeusta* L.). Omsk.

Remark. No modern materials from the territory of Omsk Region.

Tribus: SAPERDINI

70. *Saperda carcharias* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 85.

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 2♂, Listvyagi, 19,26.VIII.2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 3♂, Bolshiye Uki, at light, 21.VII.2019, 22.VII.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 9.VIII.2017, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 2♂, 3♀, Knyazev, 1.VIII.1992, 30.VI.1983, 30.VI.1982, 17.VIII.1992, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Maiskiy, 3.VII.2021, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♀, Davydovka, 4.VII.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 3♂, 1♀, Omsk, 25.VI.1997, 29.VII.1998, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♂, Kamyshino, at light, 17-18.VIII.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 3♂, 2♀, Solyanoye, 11.VII.2021, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♀, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 1990, O.N. Kholodov (OKO); 2♀, Atmas, 16.VII.2019, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 spm., Buzan, 11-12.VIII.2016, S.A. Knyazev (ISEA); 1♂, Buzan, at light, 23.VIII.2021, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 3♂, Buzan, at light, 8-9.VIII.2020, 27-28.VIII.2021, 8-9.VIII.2020, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS); 2♂, Ermak, 20, 22.VII.2015, A.A. Sal'nik (ASO).

71. *Saperda perforata* (Pallas, 1773)

Lavrov, 1927: 85. Podgorodka, Omsk.

Material examined. 3♂, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♀, Listvyagi, 9.VII.2008, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 spm., Abakshikha, 18.VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 4.VIII.2007, 30.VI.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, 10-11.VII.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 11.VI.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1 spm., Samsonovo, 2.VIII.2013, S.A. Knyazev (VTO); 3♂, 2♀, Knyazev, 25.VII.1998, 10.VI.1983, 8.VIII.1992, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Knyazev, 8.VIII.1982, K.B. Ponomarev (OGKM); 1 spm., Knyazev, 5.VII.1982, K.B. Ponomarev (ISEA); 3♂, Novovarshevka, 29-30.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS); 1♀, Atmas, 11.VII.2016, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, Buzan, 5.V.2021, 27.VIII.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Ermak, 21.VI.2017, at light, A.A. Sal'nik (ASO).

72. *Saperda scalaris* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 85.

Material examined. 1♀, Listvyagi, 2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 14.25.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2♂, Bolshiye Uki, 15.VI.2014, 5.VII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♀, Verkhniye Uki, 16.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♀, Petropavlovka, 23.VI.2007, S.A. Knyazev (SKSS); 1♂, Gulyai Pole, 19.VI.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, 2♀, Knyazevo, 22.VI.2010, 8.VII.1996, 8.VI.1994, 11.VI.1995, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, 3♀, Krutaya Gorka, ex larva, from Betula log, 8.V.2020, C.M. Saikina (SKSS).

73. *Saperda populnea* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 85

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Belogrivka, 15.VI.2018, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1 spm., Belogrivka, 16.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 9.VI.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 1♂, Knyazevo, 19.V.1982, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 4♂, 1♀, Buzan, 20–22.V.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

74. **Menesia sulphurata* (Gebler, 1825)

Material examined. 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 19.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♀, Knyazevo, 2.V.1982, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1 spm., Knyazevo, 1.VII.1982, K.B. Ponomarev (VTO); 3♂, Victory Park, 16.VI.1995, 10.VI.1995, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Atmos, 11.VII.2016, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

Tribus: PHYTOECIINI

75. *Oberea oculata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Lavrov, 1927: 85. Omsk.

Material examined. 1♀, Listvyagi, 1.VIII.2015, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 3♂, 1♀, Knyazevo, 7.VII.1998, 30.VI.1997, 9.VII.1983, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Davydovka, 4.VII.2016, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

76. **Oberea erythrocephala* (Schrank, 1776)

Material examined. 1♂, Atmos, 23.V.2016, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

77. *Phytoecia affinis* (Harrer, 1784)

Lavrov, 1927: 85. Omsk.

Material examined. 1♂, Kalmatskoye, 7.VII.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 1♀, Knyazevo, 22.VI.1996, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

78. *Phytoecia coeruleascens* (Scopoli, 1763)

Lavrov, 1927: 85 (*Phytoecia virescens* F.). Omsk.

Material examined. 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 10.VII.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 5.VI.2008, 6.VI.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 1♂, 1♀, Davy-

dovka, 3.VI.2009, S.A. Knyazev (OGKM); 1♀, Ul'zhai, 1.VI.2022, A.G. Moseiko, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♀, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 3.VI.2022, A.G. Moseiko, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♀, Atmas, 30.VI.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, Alabota, 10.VI.2008, V.G. Zaulitskaya (OGKM).

79. **Phytoecia cylindrica* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 11.VII.2008, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 6.VI.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 15.VI.2018, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 5.VI.2008, 6.VI.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO).

80. **Phytoecia icterica* (Schalber, 1783)

Material examined. 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 6.VI.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 14.VI.2009, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO).

Tribus: AGAPANTHIINI

81. **Theophilea subcylindricollis* Hladil, 1988

Material examined. Bolshiye Uki, 4.VI.2017, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO).

82. *Agapanthia dahli* (Richter, 1821)

Lavrov, 1927: 85 (*Agapanthia dahlii* Rich.). Podgorodka, Omsk.

Material examined. 5♂, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, 2006, 2007, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Abakshikha, 17.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♀, Yakovlevka, 8.VII.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 18.VI.2021, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 13,15.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 4♂, 1♀, Knyazev, 23.VI.2010, 26.VI.1982, 26.VI.1996, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Knyazev, 26.VI.1982, K.B. Ponomarev (OGKM); 1♀, Isil'kul', 5.VII.2012, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 1♀, Davydovka, 30.VI.2017, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, 2♀, Davydovka, 15.VI.2009, 15.VI.2010, S.A. Knyazev (OGKM); 1♂, 1♀, Partsyezd, 26.VI.2021, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 2♀, Andreevka, VI.2020, 9.VI.2020, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); Krasnyi Oktyabr', 1990, O.N. Kholodov (OKO); 2♂, Ul'zhai, 1.VI.2022, A.G. Moseiko, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♀, Ermak, 19.VI.2017, A.A. Sal'nik (ASO).

83. **Agapanthia villosviridescens* (De Geer, 1775)

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, V-VI.2006, V.Yu. Teploukhov (OGKM); 1♂, Yakovlevka, 8.VII.2020, V.Yu. Teploukhov (SKSS); 1 spm., Belogrivka, 16.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (ISEA); 2 spm., Bolshiye Uki, 7,16.VI.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov (VTO); 2♂, 3♀, Bolshiye Uki, 9.VII.2007, VI-VII.2014, V.Yu. Teploukhov (KPO); 1♀, Atak, 11.VI.2000, T.F. Kosheleva (OGKM); 2♀, Sedelnikovo, 7.VII.2013, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Kalmatskoye, 7.VII.2012, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 2♂, 1♀, Knyazev, 16.VII.2011, 24.VI.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 1♀, Krasnoyarka,

22.VI.1995, 3.VII.2011, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, Davydovka, 19.VI.1999, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♂, 1♀, Partsyezd, 18.VI.2022, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, 1♀, Ermak, 6.VI.2019, 29.VI.2017, A.A. Sal'nik (ASO).

Figures 4–12. 4 – *Rhagium inquisitor*, Podgorodka, ex larva, 10.II.2022, photo by S.A. Knyazev; 5 – *Brachyta interrogationis*, in copula, Bolshiye Uki, 19.VI.2016, photo by V.Yu. Teploukhov; 6 – *Lepturobosca virens*, Bolshiye Uki, 19.VIII.2014, photo by V.Yu. Teploukhov; 7 – *Pachytodes erraticus*, Partsyezd, 4.VII.2020, photo by S.M. Saikina; 8 – *Oedecnema gebleri*, Bolshiye Uki, 24.VI.2013, photo by V.Yu. Teploukhov; 9 – *Leptura annularis*, Abakshikha, 20.VI.2013, photo by V.Yu. Teploukhov; 10 – *Leptura aethiops*, Abakshikha, 20.VI.2014, photo by V.Yu. Teploukhov; 11 – *Leptura nigripes*, Bolshiye Uki, 24.VI.2013, photo by V.Yu. Teploukhov; 12 – *Arhopalus rusticus*, Petropavlovka, at light, 24.VII.2010, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figures 13–18. 13 – *Spondilis buprestoides*, Petropavlovka, at light, 24.VII.2010, photo by S.A. Knyazev; 14 – *Purpuricenus globulicollis*, Partsyezd, 26.VI.2021, photo by S.M. Saikina; 15 – *Semanotus undatus*, Podgorodka, ex larva, 22.I.2022, photo by S.A. Knyazev; 16 – *Echinocerus floralis*, Elita, 21.VI.2020, photo by S.M. Saikina; 17 – *Xylotrechus rusticus*, Partsyezd, ex larva, 22.I.2022, photo by S.A. Knyazev; 18 – *Politodorcadion politum*, in copula, Buzan, 26.IV.2020, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

84. *Agapanthiola leucaspis* (Steven, 1817)

Lavrov, 1927: 99.

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Davydovka, 12.VI.2010, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO); 1♀, Ul`zhai, 1.VI.2022, A.G. Moseiko, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, 1♀, Bolshoi Atmos, 31.V.2021, 2.VI.2022, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS); 1♂, 1♀, Cherlack station, 1.VI.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKSS).

Thus, on the territory of the Omsk region, 84 species of longicorn beetles have been established. 41 species are reported for the first time. This list is not final and will be updated during further entomological studies in the region. Most of the species mentioned in the article are illustrated on the website "Longicorn beetles of the Omsk region" at: <https://cerambycidae.omflies.ru/>

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